

Table 1. Information of SPPH cases in different midwifery institutions

		Secondary midwifery hospital (N=86)	Tertiary midwifery hospital (N=238)	P-value
Age(year)		32.9±4.5	34.2±4.5	0.02
	<35	53(61.6)	131(55)	0.31
	35-39	29(33.7)	78(32.8)	>0.99
	≥40	4(4.7)	29(12.2)	0.06
Gestational weeks(w)		38.2±3.5	36.0±3.9	<0.01
Hight(cm)		163.4±5.0	162.2±4.7	0.46
Parity	0	59(68.8)	126(52.9)	0.02
	1	24(27.9)	79(33.2)	0.42
	≥2	3(3.5)	31(13)	0.01
Delivery mode	Vaginal	38(44.2)	58(24.4)	<0.01
	Caesarean	48(55.8)	180(75.6)	
antenatal PPH risk ^a	Without risk	64(74.4)	57(23.9)	<0.01
	With risk	22(25.6)	181(76.1)	
	Placental	6(7.0)	130(54.6)	<0.01
Etiology	Tone	47(54.7)	76(31.9)	<0.01
	Tissue	13(15.1)	139(58.4)	<0.01
	Trauma	14(16.3)	11(4.6)	<0.01
	Thrombin	12(14.0)	12(5.0)	0.01
Results	Amount of bleeding (ml)	2293±1180	2325±1022	0.83
	1500-1999	43(50.0)	96(40.3)	0.13
	2000-3999	31(36.0)	123(51.7)	0.02
	≥4000	12(14.0)	19(8.0)	0.13
	Amount of Bleeding in vaginal delivery ^b	2036±838	2235±990	0.30
	< 2000	20(52.6)	21(36.2)	0.14
	2000-3999	17(44.7)	32(55.2)	0.40
	≥4000	1(2.6)	5(8.6)	0.40
	Amount of Bleeding in CS ^c	2494±1362	2371±1055	0.49
	< 2000	23(47.9)	75(41.7)	0.51
	2000-3999	14(29.2)	91(50.6)	0.01
	≥4000	11(22.9)	14(7.8)	0.01
	Admission to ICU	14(16.3)	135(56.7)	<0.01
	PPH complications	40(46.5)	49(20.6)	<0.01
	Coagulation disorders	34(39.5)	31(13)	<0.01
	Shock	18(20.9)	28(11.8)	0.047
	Kidney damage	6(7.0)	9(3.8)	0.24
	Cardiopulmonary function disorders	5(5.8)	7(2.9)	0.31
Transfusion	Rbc (u)	8.7±5.1	8.1±4.5	0.26

	≤4	14(16.3)	51(21.4)	0.35
	4.1-10	47(54.7)	117(49.2)	0.45
	>10	25(29.1)	69(29)	>0.99
	Max	24	28	
	Plasma (ml)	1015±781	832±531	0.01
	< 1000	52(60.5)	168(70.6)	0.11
	1000-2000	25(29.1)	52(21.8)	0.19
	>2000	7(8.1)	15(6.3)	0.62
	Max	4600	4000	
PPH management	Intraoperative approaches ^c			
	B-lynch suture	9(18.8)	46(25.6)	0.45
	Artery ligation	9(18.8)	41(22.8)	0.70
	Hysterectomy	0(0.0)	43(23.9)	<0.01
	Packing in CS	14(29.2)	14(7.8)	<0.01
	Transarterial embolization	1(1.2)	26(10.9)	<0.01
	Unscheduled return to the OR	18(20.9)	18(7.6)	<0.01
	Unplanned exploratory laparotomy	9(10.5)	17(7.1)	0.36
	Unplanned hysterectomy	2(2.3)	7(2.9)	>0.99

Data were presented as n (%) or mean±SD

^a antenatal PPH risk: 1. Placenta previa, placenta accreta; 2. Prior uterine surgery history (over 2 times CS or myomectomy); 3. Intramural fibroid (≥ 5 cm); 4. Multiple pregnancy; 5. Macrosomia; 6. Previous PPH history; 7. Anticoagulant medication/coagulation disorders (Fib/platelet reduce); 8. Severe PE or HELLP; 9. Anemia (Hb ≤ 9.0 g/dL).

^b percentage is based on the account of vaginal deliveries

^c percentage is based on the account of Cesarean section deliveries